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Scientific Study :(Solutions and Recommendations to Avoid the Spread of Corona Virus Covid 19 in Iraq)

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Abstract

This case study to solve social scientific problem in Iraq and world like spread of infection, that described some suggestions and solutions to reduce the spread of corona virus infection, especially among children and the elderly, who have immune system problems, heart diseases and respiratory diseases, in addition to finding solutions of the infection Problem :

Name Problem: Scientific Study for Treatment of Scientific-Social Problem (spread of corona virus.19).

Type of Study: Scientific Study for Treatment of Scientific-Social Problem (spread of corona virus.19).

Aim of Scientific Study: Finding solutions of spread of corona virus. 19.

Key words: Cov.19, Sars Corona Virus19, Social Problem, Corona Virus, Scientific Study, Case Study, Social Problem.

Introduction

Corona viruses cause a large proportion of common cases in the elderly and children. Corona virus causes colds with major symptoms, such as fever and swollen appendages, especially in people in winter and early spring. Symptoms begin with a rise in body temperature and then coughing, which are symptoms that affect most of us in the winter. But the virus can cause an overreaction of the immune system. One of the most serious symptoms is severe respiratory distress caused by pneumonia. The inflammation is a sign that you must fight the infection and repair its spoils. This is simply the cause of wound infections, but inside the body the situation becomes more complicated. The virus causes inflammation in the body parts, respectively, and these organs cannot play their normal role".The lungs are unable to get enough oxygen and carbon dioxide from the blood. It can prevent the kidneys from cleaning blood and damaging the lining of the intestine.

Corona pneumonia viruses may cause viral pneumonia either directly or secondary with bacterial pneumonia. It may also cause bronchitis, whether viral bronchitis directly or secondary to bacterial bronchitis. The spread of the Human Corona virus in 2003

was the Corona virus associated with severe acute respiratory syndrome (the Corona virus associated with SARS syndrome), which causes severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), and has a unique pathogenic potential, there are seven strains of Human Corona virus:

- Corona Human Virus 229E (HCoV-229E).
- Corona Human Virus OC43 (HCoV-OC43).
- Corona syndrome virus (SARS-CoV).
- SK NL63 (HCoV-NL63).
- SKU1 human virus
- Corona Virus Associated with Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV), formerly known as New Corona Virus 2012 (HCoV-EMC).
- Corona Emerging Virus (2019-nCoV), known as Wuhan pneumonia or Wuhan Corona virus. (newly discovered)

Corona Virus (CoV 2019)

The virus was believed to be the origin of the virus, but many prominent researchers disagreed with this belief. The virus is 96% similar to corona virus, so it is widely believed to be of bat origin.

The virus was first discovered in Wuhan, central China, in December 2019. It is believed to have originated in wild animals and has spread to humans by mixing infected animals during wildlife trade operations in wet markets. The virus then spread to other Chinese provinces in early and mid-January 2020 due to the Chinese New Year holidays. Infected cases have started to appear in other countries, due to the transmission of the disease through international travel.

Figure 1

Corona's Effect on the Elderly

The elderly are considered to be the group exposed to Corona virus and the fastest infection in them, as the high mortality rate of the elderly has made public opinion (that the disease kills the elderly and does not recover from it except in rare cases of these cases, unlike young people, what led doctors in Spain and Italy to set conditions for receiving patients excluding the elderly. The Centers for Disease Control says that "the elderly" and people with acute chronic disease are more likely to develop severe illness due to Covid-19.

People over the age of 80 may want to be extra careful. A report published in the medical journal "JAMA" which examined more than 72,000 Chinese patients infected with the virus, found that the overall death rate was 2.3%. But among adults over 80, the death rate has risen to 15%. If you live in a community where the disease has spread, you are more likely to become infected as well.

Figure 2

Corona's Effect on the Children

Despite the outbreaks of new virus corona virus, it appears that the new epidemic does not affect children in general, and if they do in rare cases, they do not suffer from severe complications, a pattern similar to previous epidemics that moved away from children. The outbreak, which began in China, has infected more than 28,200 people worldwide, according to the Associated Press, Thursday, nearly

60 days after the first case appeared in early December. But according to health experts, the virus does not usually infect children, as "the average age of patients is between 49 and 56 years", according to a report published on Wednesday in "Gamma", the American Journal of Medicine, noting that "cases in children are rare." In one case, a 10-year-old boy traveled to Wuhan, the epidemic outbreak, with his family, and upon his return to Shenzhen, other infected family members, aged between 36 to 66, had fever, sore throat, diarrhea and pneumonia, while he was not injured. The child had any visible external symptoms, but he had vision, inflammation, according to the New York Times. Doctors then expected that the absence of signs of fever and external disease was the model for infecting children with the Corona virus.

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Figure 3

Solutions of Infection Problem

There are a few solutions around how to break and stop the infection: There are a few solutions around how to reducing of corona virus spread via The Chemical Sterilization, before proceeding with sterilization chemicals, consider whether there is a more appropriate method than chemical sterilization, where chemical sterilization is used only with tools that are damaged by heat at high costs of applying the "one-time use" unilateral use of these tools. Equipment and tools can be sterilized by dipping them in a chemical solution, leaving them for a while and then rinsing with sterile water. The immersion period continues for an appropriate time, depending on the type of material used for sterilization, in order to result in the killing (bacterial spores) Sterilization of all airports and places of gathering with sterile materials and chemical disinfectants, sterilization of toilets, sanitation facilities, and surfaces in homes and hospitals, food, utensils, and all daily-use tools and towels The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention advises against unnecessary travel by plane for the elderly.

Figure 4

Figure 5

It is wise to stay away from cruise ships at the present time as well. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention said that cruise passengers are at increased risk of transmission from person to person in all narrow places, so if you have already developed cruise plans, it is best to cancel them. Wearing protective masks and paws on a

Figure 6

continuous basis, especially when leaving the house and wearing protective and sterile clothes. On return, they must be disposed of and wash clothes on a daily basis and using detergents and disinfectants for this purpose. Using sterilizers to wash hands continuously,

Figure 7

especially when touching tools of permanent and general use, and

using sterilizers that do not cause harm and irritation of the respiratory system in children

Figure 8

Recommendations

The following suggestions may contribute forward to recover solutions the infection:

- Disinfection of floors and surfaces.
- Wearing paws and gags.
- Not leaving the house too often.
- Avoid crowds and crowded places.
- Wash hands frequently after touching things.
- Avoid shaking, kissing, and walking away one and a half meters when talking to anyone.
- Block flights.
- The affected person stays at home so that he does not spread the infection to others.
- Cover your mouth and nose with a tissue when you cough or sneeze, then throw it in the trash and wash your hands.
- Surface cleaning and disinfection. Follow hygiene measures, including washing hands regularly before and after touching animals, and avoid contact with sick animals.
- Avoid consuming raw or uncooked animal products, including milk and meat, because consuming them increases the chance of infection, and for camel milk and meat it can be eaten but after pasteurization, cooking, or other thermal treatments.

Conclusions

The virus was believed to be the origin of the virus, but many prominent researchers disagreed with this belief. The virus is 96% similar to corona virus, so it is widely believed to be of bat origin. Sterilization of all airports and places of gathering with sterile materials and chemical disinfectants, to control of infection: sterilization of toilets, sanitation facilities, and surfaces in homes and hospitals, food, utensils, and all daily-use tools and towels

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